

Psalm 82

"God and Consolation"

This is not a psalm of consolation.

Why would it be?

Consolation is needed when
there is no way left, no hope.

But there is always hope.

And there is always a way.

For there is always God.

And if one is, from the heart,
obedient to Him — out of love,
not out of duty, but
out of respect and reverence;
if one is upright,
sincere, honest, and trusting,
holding fast to faith,
steadfast in belief,
courageous and firm,
then there is always hope,
and God is always there.

For if God is love,
then He is at home here.

And should I be mistaken,
and there be only eternal sleep,
even then would I
still want to be here,
still want to believe
only this.

For if there is no God,
then I see no meaning in
being eternal.

Truth is closer to a fairy tale
than to what we call
reality ...

(from the new Psalms – The Way of the Open Heart)